

Corpus-Based Investigation of Explicitation Shifts in Self-Translation

Correspondence:

Ansa Sattar
<ansa.sattar@gcuf.edu.pk>

PhD Scholar, Department of Applied Linguistics, Government College University, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

Prof. Dr. Muhammad Asim Mahmood
<masimmahmood@gcuf.edu.pk>

Chairperson, Department of Applied Linguistics, Government College University, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

Publication details:

Received: October 25, 2022

Accepted: December 20, 2022

Published: December 30, 2022

Abstract

The study examines explicitation shifts in the translation of the novel "Perfect Mentor" from its source text in Urdu (ST) to its target text (TT). Explicitation is the process of making something clear and unambiguous, divided into two levels: substitution and addition. The study used a corpus-based methodology and a valid framework for investigating explicitation shifts in the text. Results are presented both quantitatively and qualitatively, showing that obligatory explicitation leads to a uniform and understandable TT, while optional explicitation may have both positive and negative impacts on the TT's style and added elements. Pragmatic explicitation was found to be neutral. To avoid awkward structures and misunderstandings, the translator must strive to maintain a balanced text and appropriate use of explicitness strategies, considering the language typology.

Keywords: explicitation analysis, substitutions, additions, obligatory shifts, optional shifts, pragmatic shifts

1. Introduction

This study counts and analyses explicitation shifts in a corpus of Urdu-English translations of Pakistani literary texts. The study's goal is to determine why there are explicitation shifts in both corpora and why the translator explicates the text. However, explicitation phenomena in Urdu to English translation have yet to be discovered, and the current study would be the first to describe them in the most recent literary master piece collection of four novels and their translations, which is representative of Pakistan's most recent literature. Many studies have been conducted, including comparative and contrastive analyses of English explicitation in comparison to other languages, but no significant study has been conducted to compare the explicitation of Pakistani English and Urdu texts in terms of explicitness. As a result, the purpose of this study is to look into the explanation diversity in Pakistani English literary texts. The phenomenon of explicitation and implicitation in translation studies was introduced by Vinay and Darbelnet (1958) and further investigated by a number of translation scholars in almost all of the world's languages. A number of studies have claimed to provide evidence for explicitation, particularly after scholars adopted corpus linguistics instruments in their investigations of explicitation and implicitation (Vestergaard, 2017). Explicitation and implicitation have given rise to a vast array of studies involving numerous language pairs and languages, an enumeration of which here would certainly be incomplete (Baker, 1993, p. 243).

Krüger (2013) conducted research on the cognitive aspects of explicitation and implicitation in scientific and technical translation. Boal (2009) conducted a study of a short story in Spanish translation in terms of explicitation and implicitation in narrative. Similarly, Konalová (2007), who has investigated explicitation and implicitation in the domain of syntax and tested Blum's (1986) hypothesis, Another factor that would make the study more fascinating is that it does not intend to test the explicitation hypothesis, because it is not much motivated in the latest translation studies, but it would identify a different factor like the influence of explicitation on translation and communication quality, and moreover, it would compare the literary translators and their style of explicating the text to make the reader more visible, clear, and friendly.

2. Review of Literature

Translation studies is a wider area in applied linguistics, and it has certain translation strategies and universals to deal with real translation, so it is necessary to describe the association of explicitation as a main strategy or universal in translation studies. This instructional approach has a long history in the field of translation studies. Translation studies emerged as a rich and fascinating paradigm of inquiry (Malmkjær & Windle, 2012). There are many different areas or types of translation studies, and as a result, other linguistic disciplines such as sociolinguistics, corpus linguistics, computer linguistics, and discourse analysis have also improved this multidimensional science. Translation studies gradually gained full recognition as a distinct academic field to which other linguistic fields might contribute. Research in translation studies is a relatively new field because it was only recently that translation and interpretation studies began to grow. This illustrates how explicitation can be a significant subject of study in translation studies.

As a result, this study is the first to look at explicit language usage in Urdu and English in Pakistan. According to Proshina (2008), scholars focused heavily on translation studies in the second half of the 20th century, which are frequently referred to as translation theories, the science of translation, the linguistics of translation, or translatology. The word "translation" was first used in English in 1340 and was derived from the Latin word "translatio," which was used in the classical French version. Since the word "transporting" was likewise created from the word "transfer" (Munday, 2016).

According to Munday, translation is a specialised procedure between two languages that entails developing and converting what is presented in the source text (ST) and the target text (TT). Since over a century ago, translation studies have been taught as a formal field in colleges and universities. Its primary feature is the abundance of scholars who study various translation-related topics (Toury, 1995, p. 1). Major translation studies research fields were illustrated by Williams and Chesterman (2002), and more areas may fall under these primary components. These themes were primarily put forth by Holms (1988a, 2004) and include such broad categories as text analysis and translation, translation quality assessment, specialised translations (such as audiovisual translations), history, translation ethics and

interpretation, and glossaries. According to these primary domains, explicitation is included in the paradigm of text analysis in translation, as well as text management and quality evaluation methodologies.

Translation studies cover a variety of topics, including translation strategies. According to Tardzenyuy (2016), many scholars, including new and seasoned researchers as well as those learning the language, refer to translation approaches, strategies, methods, or processes. These terminologies have shifting meanings as well, and these shifting interpretations of translation techniques can be specific or widespread. Translation techniques are employed as an operational procedure by the translators to carry out genuine translation (Tardzenyuy, 2016). In layman's terms, these are the more specific methods that translators employ to carry out the more fundamental, generally accepted translation plan. Tardzenyuy considered explicitation to be a key translation approach when anything in the source language text (SLT) needed to be clarified or some information was inferred in the target language text (ST).

Hatim and Munday (2004) highlighted that text management, or regular divergence from literal translation and dynamic equivalence, is a necessary feature for better translation because the translation depends on three major tactics for dealing with text in translation. These strategies can go in a variety of directions, as Nida (1964, p. 139) notes that a translator may move toward expanding details or explicitation in order to sustain the text, which may result in a condensed and complex translation. Additionally, this may entail frequently repeating the facts in TT or assuming the meanings, which is a highly effective method for languages with significantly greater amounts of semantic repetition (Munday, 2016). Explicitation was demonstrated as an additional translation technique that is essential for every standard translation, especially since Vinay and Darbelnet presented it.

Pym (2014) also discussed translation methods and how explicitation, which has the potential to offer specification for information that is not explicitly provided in the ST, can bring natural equivalence to the translation as well. Pym provided concrete examples of the many approaches and answers that Vinay and Darbelnet had specifically described in 1958. Proshina (2008) stated that when lexical modifications are made during translation, the translation's semantic perspective is altered. The explicitation method is one of the "explicitation" translation methods. This shows that explicitation is a significant topic of translation studies, and the current study's goal is to evaluate explicitation primarily as an initiative in the translation from Urdu to Pakistani.

Similar to this, Lev (2011) stated that a translator's main focus while translating a literary work is to elaborate it in the target language text (TLT), making it easier to understand by offering it in an easier form or representation. Information in the ST is frequently greatly influenced by such a major objective. The ST is also explained by translators. Since translators do more than just translate the content, they also need to elaborate on it and make it easier for readers to understand. While translating, translators also make use of logic and connections, occasionally finish them off correctly, and add additional cognitive elements. The method of idea representation and its explication can typically be made less creative in this process by translators. By adjusting three translation techniques—creating logical TT, making missing ST aspects explicit, and formalising grammatical links—they are able to solve this issue and make it more cognitive.

According to Levy's argument, explicitation is more important during the actual translation process. This study is the first to look at the explicitation phenomenon in Pakistani translation. Additionally, Levys explained that in order to save the content in TT, translators frequently struggle to define terms that are not explicitly stated in the ST for their local language readers. Simply by creating the opposite of its ST, they can demonstrate how essential but undetermined events in the ST can have more explicit meanings when they are determined in the TT.

Toury (1977) provided an illustration of the potential for translation universals. According to Toury, it is possible that translators will explain or elaborate on the translation information provided implicitly in the ST, regardless of translation register, genre, or language history. The statement demonstrates that translation academics thought of it as a universal technique or universal of translation studies prior to its thorough investigation. Since explicitation is a universal behaviour, many scholars also regard it as a technique for creating meaning in translation. For example, Vandepitte (2013) discussed creating meaning in translation by illustrating how the level of explicitation of a spoken or written expression can affect how its meaning can be defined. As several scholars investigate explicitation as a translation universal or meaning-making strategy, this element has been gained in numerous translation discoveries. In translation studies, the meanings in TT are also shown to be either explicit or implicit. The assertions describe the importance and connection of translation studies within translation studies as well as how various academics view it in terms of practical translation practises and research projects. Explicitation is a crucial occurrence in translation studies, and the current study is the first to analyse it using data in Urdu and English.

3. Material and Methods

Klaudy's (2008) classification is used as a framework to extract the shifts of explicitation in literary texts. Klaudy listed four types of explicitation: obligatory, optional, pragmatic, and translation-inherent. Obligatory explicitation includes syntactic explicitation and semantic explicitation. This type of explicitation is dictated by differences in morphological, syntactic, and/or semantic structures between languages. Without obligatory explicitation, TT will not conform to the grammatical norms of TL. On the other hand, optional explicitation depends on language use. It is determined by TT stylistic preferences, which may lead a translator to produce grammatically correct and natural, native-like sentences. Both obligatory and optional explicitation typically involve the insertion of linguistic elements, which is a consequence of the concretization, separation, and/or addition of SL lexical or grammatical items. Pragmatic explicitation commonly corresponds to cultural explicitation and occurs to supplement possible cultural gaps between source and target cultures. Pragmatic explicitation often involves translators' adding explanations to implicit cultural information or to concepts that do not exist in the target language. The last classification of explicitation—translation-inherent explicitation—is language-independent and depends on the nature of the translation process itself. This type of explicitation has nothing to do with structural, formal, or stylistic differences between SL and TL, nor with culture-specific textual elements.

3.1 Data collection

The data is collected methodically, beginning with Urdu and English novels, and is obtained in hard copy form from Ferozsons' publishers in Lahore. The hard data is then scanned with a camscanner, and the scanned literary data is converted into editable and cleaned form using optical character recognition. The data obtained from OCR was not entirely correct; it was proofread to ensure the text's validity. The corpus data is a lengthy piece of literature that can provide reliable quantitative results in the form of explicitation shifts in TT as compared to ST.

3.2 Parallel Corpora Compilation

The text files are maintained for the tagging procedure to make the parallel corpora. The Urdu tagging is done by Stanford Postagger 3.5.2, and English POS tagging is done with Multidimensional Analysis Tagger 1.3. After the tagging process, the corpus data is arranged in sequence to mark the shifts by reading the text. The reliability of the data collection procedure and parallel corpus compilation is maintained according to the corpus and previous studies' principles.

3.3 UAM Corpus Tool

The data is incorporated in the UAM Corpus Tool, first selecting the option of extended corpus and then browsing the respective Unicode file in the application. A file first appears in the lower box after being uploaded and is further incorporated into the main window (by selecting the option “Incorporate All”) for coding. Using a cyclic approach, a comprehensive scheme is provided to the software in order to tag the text. Scheme is of major concern, but it is not everything, as the context of words tagged defines and redefines their categories, so a process of rectification is carried out manually. Scheme is developed and edited by selecting the option of layers in the UAM software and then selecting the option of adding a layer.

Source: The Authors

Figure 1. Framework of Study

4. Discussion

4.1 Research Background

This research aims to analyse explication in the Urdu novel *Peer-e-Kamil* as source text and its English translation, “The Perfect Mentor,” as target text. The research undertook corpus-based and UAM software-based methodologies to investigate the occurrences of explication in target text as compared to the source text. UAM software is used to highlight the types of explication by developing a manual scheme according to the occurrences of explication shifts. The most highlighted research in the area is by Becher (2011), particularly on explication analysis by Robin (2014) and Acker (2018).

These researchers worked on explication in other languages, and they contributed mainly to increasing the literature on explication. They also declared it a significant translation strategy by using different wording and context. The present research used Klaudy’s (2010) classification of explication as a framework and undertook two methods: corpus-based methodology and UAM software-based statistical results. The researcher first compiled the two corpora separately, after which a parallel corpus was compiled and explication shifts were investigated manually by reading the features further calculated through UAM software according to the developed scheme. The classification was used with or without any modification in the previous research. The corpus-based methodology undertaken for the analysis was previously used by many researchers and proved reliable (Becher, 2011; Robin, 2014; Acker, 2019), but UAM software is used for the first time for the analysis of explication along with manual and corpus-based methodology for reliable and valid results.

4.2 Feature Explication in TT

Our results showed the involvement of all grammatical features in highlighting the explication in the target text. The parallel corpora showed explication on nouns, pronouns, verbs, adverbs, adjectives, and at conjunction level.

4.2.1 Noun Based Shifts

Addition and substitution of nominal materials that have been identified in the investigated data. Researchers found multiple occurrences where translators substituted nouns.

4.2.1.1 Substitution of Noun

Explication of Noun	
Substitution	38
Addition	12

جویریہ | PN بے | PN اختیار | NN ہنسی | NN

TT: Javeria_ NNP burst_ NN out_ IN laughing_ VBG

4.2.1.2 Addition of Noun

The researcher discovered an instance where the addition of a noun (situation) in the target text, apart from noun-verb substitutions, improved the context and clarity. There was a total of 12 counted noun additions. Some shifts were found where a noun was replaced with a personal pronoun in the target text. The analysis of the parallel corpora examined 38 occurrences of noun substitution and 10 instances of noun addition.

جویریہ | PN نے | P جیسے | A صفائی | NN پیش | NN کرنے | VB کی | P کو | P شش | NN کی

TT: Javeria_ NNP tried_ VBD to_ TO redeem_ VB the_ DT situation_ NN

4.2.2 Adjective Based Shifts

Adjectives played a vital role in constructing the appropriate meaning in the process of translation. 38 occurrences of adjective substitution and 10 occurrences of adjective addition are investigated in the parallel corpora. Extensive use of adjectives enhances the informativeness and intelligibility of English target texts.

Adjective	
Substitution	38
Addition	10

بے | PN فکری | NN اور | CC لاپرواہی | NN

TT: unconcerned_ JJ and_ CC nonchalant_ JJ

The investigated example shows the substitution of a noun with an adjective, both of which are connected by a coordinating conjunction. The addition of an adjective has the same effect on translation as this type of substitution. Frequent shifts are calculated where nouns are substituted with adjectives in the TT.

وہ | PP بلا | ADV کی | P حاضر | ADJ جواب | NN تھی | VB

TT: she_ PRP was_ VBD so_ RB quick-witted_ JJ and_ CC vivacious_ JJ

In the preceding example, optional explicitation is accomplished by adding the adjective "vivacious" (JJ) to strengthen or focus on the stated statement in order to assure the reader about the novel character optionally added this adjective here.

4.2.3 Verb Based Shift

Substitution of verb and noun is higher in proportion. The addition of nominal material is necessary to fill the argument slot. 47 instances of verb substitution and 16 occurrences of verb addition are counted. Progressive verbs are extensively used where on-going processes are reported. Actually, translators are forced to use progressive verbs like "turning out," "talking to," and "healing with."

4.2.3.1 Substitution of Verb

ST: ایک | CA ہی | I سانس | NN میں | P وہ | PP دوہ | NN پی | VB آگیا | AA

TT: gulped_ VBD it_ PRP down_ RP

Substitution always helps in terms of economy of space, like in this sentence, where one single verb replaces the complete meaning and context in an appropriate way.

Verb	
Substitution	47
Addition	16

4.2.3.2 Addition of Verb

TT: teenagers_ NNS were_ VBD roaring_ VBG around_ IN the_ DT city

Additions of verb were not much frequent in the target text.

4.2.4 Adverb Based Shifts

The proportion of adverbs is lower as compared to other features; English has a lower capacity to accommodate optional adverbials. The translator might have decided to avoid stylistically awkward clustering of sentence initial adverbials because the researcher did not find any initial instances of adverbs. All counted occurrences are in the middle or at the end.

Adverb	
Substitution	18
Addition	9

ST: بولے | VB بلائے | NN سر | P میں | NN انداز | ADJ قطعی

TT: shook_ VBD her_ PRP\$ head_ NN decisively_ RB

4.2.4.1 Addition of Adverb

TT: Non-chalantly, distractedly, distastefully, repeatedly

Researcher made it successful to find out the few instances of adverbial addition.

4.3 Reasons of Explicitation of the Features in TT

Explicitation of the above-mentioned features is more frequent in the target text, and it occurs for certain reasons that have been observed by previous researchers in their studies of explicitation. The first reason is to precisely clarify the information in the target text. Reason for multiple additions in the target text is due to language typology because there is no exact alternative to the source text expression in the target text. The target language lacks the same syntactic structure as the source language, which is a third and more valid reason.

The first reason reveals that the translator wanted to convey every bit of information in the target text that is given in the source text. The source text contains details that the translator thought should be delivered appropriately to avoid misunderstandings and misleading

information. An example from the text can show the information in both TT and ST. Another interesting reason for explicitation is that literary translators always have a good capacity to explicate the context, like:

ST: وہ | PP | NN | NN | سے | SE | ADJ | ADJ | ADJ | NN | میں | P | VB | گئی | AA | تھی | TA | اور | CC | RP | وہ | PP | ایک | CA | بار | NN | ADV | NN | تھا | NN | میں | P | آگیا | NN | NN |

TT: IN if_ IN she_ PRP had_ VBD raced_ VBN overnight_ RB from_ IN teenage_ JJ to_ TO middle_ JJ age_ NN and_ CC he_ PRP had_ VBD regressed_ VBN to_ TO his_ PRP pre-teens_ NNS

The second reason describes that explicitation happens when lexical items given in the source text do not have an appropriate alternative in the target text. In this parallel corpus analysis, many examples are highlighted where the translator was not able to substitute language expressions in TT. Most translators have a general tendency to maximise explicitness by using more precise lexical features. To avoid misleading and misunderstanding, the translator regularly explicates the translation by substituting.

ST: | PP | کوئی | Q | دو | CA | چار | CA | سال | NN | کا | P | بچہ | NN | نہیں | NEG | ہوں | VB | کہ | SC | میرے | G | آگے | NN | چھپے | NN | پھرنا | VB | پڑے | AA | آپ | PP | کو | P

TT: I_ PRP am_ VBP not_ RB a_ DT four-year-old_ JJ who_ WP you_ PRP need_ VBP to_ TO nag

The reason for lexical item explicitation and implicitation is also found in Becher's (2011) study of nouns, pronouns, adjectives, adverbs, connectors, and conjunctions. According to the results, these features showed a relatively lower number of implicitations and a higher proportion of explicitations (Robin 2014).

4.4 Effect of Frequent Explicitation on the TT

The distribution of explicitation types is illustrated below. A higher proportion of optional articulation is investigated. Parallel corpora revealed that frequent optional explicitation has a number of positive and negative effects on the target text when compared to the source text.

TYPES_OF_EXPLICIATION-TYPE	N=161	
Obligatory explicitation	56	34.78
Optional explicitation	91	56.52
Pragmatic explicitation	14	8.70

4.4.1 Sense Conversion and Change in TT

When the source text expression is complete in the novel situation while reading, the discourse is optionally omitted and sometimes presented in a completely different form. Many instances were discovered by the researchers that could not be properly translated in TT.

in this sentence writer tries to convey that on new year night teenagers and group of boys roaring around the city and streets on their motorbikes by performing different stunts and they grouped together to reach a hall and the moment they enter started dancing making noise taunting people and lot many other stuff they have gone through. Translated text is not conveying this sense appropriately like Lights_ NNS off_ IN meant_ VBD a_ DT display_ NN of_ IN complete_ JJ abandon_ VBP. Translator optionally substitute actual sense of understanding.

Another example from data describes the sense of change in the target text. *کئی | P | پر | NN | پھرے | P | کے | NN | لڑکے | ADJ | دیگرے | NN | بعد | ADJ | یکے* | translated as The_ DT boy_ NN 's face_ NN changed_ VBD a_ DT myriad_ JJ colors_ NNS here. The plethora of colours in this example do not correspond to the sense (annoyance, fear, or confusion) presented in the source text. Target text cannot justify the feeling of the boy who was instructed by the teacher to draw a diagram and label it as a punishment for not focusing on the lecture during class.

4.4.2 Complex Translation

Excessive optional explicitation made the text compact for proficient speakers, but optional substitutions became complicated for medium and less-medium second language readers. Frequent instances were investigated that need simple translation but translator made them complex by optionally substitute and add lexico-grammatical features. Examples are like *یوں | AP | لگ | VB | آ رہا | AA | تھا | TA | جیسے | TA | وہ | A | وہ | PP | پہلی | OR | ہاں | NN | وہاں | AP | آیا | VB | تھا | TA* translated as It_ PRP seemed_ VBD that_ IN this_ DT was_ VBD his_ PRP first_ JJ venture_ NN into_ IN this_ DT domain_ NN in this example translator optionally added two nouns venture and domain into the target text to make it complex for the reader. It can be translated easily in a simple way, like "it seemed like he came here for the first time."

The second example is also showing the complexity of target text as compared to source text.

کیو | PN | تک | SC | وہاں | AP | پر | P | ان | PP | میں | P | سے | SE | بھی | I | کم | ADJ | عمر | NN | لڑ | VB | کے | P | آتے | VB | تھے | TA | اور | CC | اہر | ADJ | کلاس | NN | اس | PD | علاقے | NN | کے | P | تھی | ADJ | شامل | P | میں | PN | ز | NN | کسٹمر | ADJ | مستقل

In the source text writer described the situation of heera mandi where she mentioned the age group of people and also mentioned the classes who are frequently visit the area. This sentence is translated as young_ JJ boys_ NNS often_ RB frequented_ VBD the_ DT area_ NN and_ CC the_ DT elite_ NN were_ VBD among_ IN the_ DT most_ RBS regular_ JJ customers_ NNS. The translator optionally added the verb frequented here to make it complex but attractive for the reader.

4.4.3 Novelty in the Target Text

A higher proportion of optional explicitation made the text compact but also introduced novelty in the target text. The optional explicitation enhanced the number of details in the novel and also optionally changed the structure, which altered the situation in literary text.

waved_ VBN away_ RB

racing_ VBG recklessly_ RB,

Groping_VBG his_PRP way_NN,
 the_DT effect_NN on_IN him_PRP was_VBD not_RB so_RB pronounced_JJ
 do_VBP n't_RB pester_VB me_PRP with_IN your_PRP silly_JJ advice_NN

These expressions are investigated in the target text only, but their context is inferable for the reader. These chunks are not given in the source text.

4.4.4 Stylistically Attractive Text Production

Optional explicitation contributes to having a positive impact on TT. The translator intended to provide stylistically pleasing TT that is appealing to native speakers while also containing language that is both interesting and challenging to the reader. Optionally adding and substituting certain features made the language compact, complex, and attractive as well. For example, four_CD weeks_NNS that is explicitly suitable English expression but different from the source text Urdu expression ایک |CA| NN in literal translation, one can say one month but translator made the language eye catching for the target reader.

Few other instances clear the perspective like لڑکے |NN| اس |PD| وقت |NN| تک |P| نشے |NN| میں |P| پوری |ADJ| طرح |NN| دعت |NN| کا |NN| پر |P| اوندھے |VB| سیدھے |ADJ| پڑے |AA| تھے |TA| translated as boys_NNS lay_VBD around_RP on_IN the_DT carpet_NN totally_RB intoxicated_VBN and_CC unaware_JJ of_IN themselves_PRP this sentence can be translated in a simple way but totally intoxicated added stylistic flavor that is more attractive and inferable to the all readers.

One more expression found like کچھ |Q| دس |NN| کر لیتا |VB| ہے |TA| اپنی |GR| مصروفیات |NN| کے |P| بارے |NN| میں |P| ہی |I| کچھ |Q| بتا دیتا |ADJ| ہے |VB| - translated as discuss_VB something_NN Talk_NN to_TO each_DT other_JJ about_IN what_WP interests_NNS us_PRP what_WP keeps_VBZ us_PRP busy_JJ. The translator optionally added what interests us just to make the reader infer that the information is appropriate and more attractive. Extensive occurrences of optional explicitation also display a positive effect on the translation in terms of stylistics.

4.4.5 Overall Meaning Communication in the TT

The results and examples demonstrated that obligatory explicitation presented a positive impact on meaning communication because it provided proper context and situations as presented in the source language. As far as optional explicitation is concerned, it seemed to have both a positive and negative impact. In terms of substitution, the translator handled the sense meaning and structure tactfully, attempting to make it appealing and authenticated, but in terms of additions, the target text became lengthy and exaggerated, with only a few instances of optional addition. Pragmatic explicitation was found to be neutral because researchers rarely found pragmatic shifts, and those shifts are inferable for the reader according to context.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that the quality of translation can be maintained by utilising the explicitation strategies in a balanced way. To reduce the structural awkwardness, maintain the style and communication, and also minimise the risk of misunderstanding, the translator needs to put in extra effort to keep a careful balance in the use of text explicitness strategies according to language typology. However, translators can achieve perfect translation by reducing the occurrences of optional explicitation shifts and making them mandatory, thereby bridging the cultural communication gap. Obligatory explicitation contributed to providing uniformly improved and inferable target text because it did not allow the translator to translate a sentence or lexical feature that was against the target language typology or more difficult to translate literally. The present study showed that translators explicate the target text for many reasons.

- When co-reference relations are implicitly given in the source text, they are not inferable in the target language.
- The target language offers a lexical item that suits the context but is not available in the source text.
- in order to comply with the typical communicative preferences of target language readers.
- following the general strategy of maximising explicitness in order to minimise misunderstanding.
- to bridge the cultural gap between different cultures.

In Pakistan, researchers can look into how translation can be made more reliable in terms of quantity and quality. In order to improve the quality of translation in Pakistan, future researchers can work in this area to look into all of these paradigms in different kinds of data.

Funding: This study was not funded in any shape or form by any party.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Bio-note:

Ansa Sattar is a PhD Scholar and a lecturer in the department of Applied Linguistics, Government College University Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. Her areas of interests are sociolinguistics, translation studies, corpus linguistics, and world Englishes.

Prof. Dr. Muhammad Asim Mahmood is Chairperson of the Department of Applied Linguistics, Government College University, Faisalabad. He is also serving as dean of social sciences and arts and humanities. His areas of interest are corpus linguistics, world Englishes, translation studies, and natural language processing.

References

- Acker, A.V. (2018). *A Corpus-based Study of Explicitation and Implication of the Connective 'Therefore' in Translation*, (Masters Dissertation).
- Blum-Kulka, S. (1986). Shifts of cohesion and coherence in translation. In *Julian House & Shoshana Blum-Kulka (eds.), Interlingual and Intercultural communication*, pp. 17–35. Tübingen: Gunter Narr.
- Baker, M. (2019). Corpus Linguistics and Translation Studies*: Implications and applications. In *Researching Translation in the Age of Technology and Global Conflict*, pp. 9-24. Routledge.
- Becher, V. (2011). *Explicitation and implication in translation. A corpus-based study of English-German and German-English translations of business texts* (Doctoral dissertation, Staats-und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg Carl von Ossietzky).

- Holm, J. A. (1988). *Pidgins and creoles: Volume 2, reference survey* (Vol. 2). Cambridge University Press.
- Holmes, J. S. (Ed.). (2011). *The nature of translation: Essays on the theory and practice of literary translation*, (Vol. 1). Walter de Gruyter.
- Hatim, B., & Munday, J. (2019). *Translation: An advanced resource book for students*. Routledge.
- Krüger, R. (2013). A cognitive linguistic perspective on explicitation and implicitation in scientific and technical translation. *Trans-kom. Journal of Translation and Technical Communication Research* 6 (2), pp. 285-314.
- Konšalová, P. (2007). Explicitation as a universal in syntactic de/condensation. *Across Languages and Cultures*, 8(1), pp. 17–32.
- Klaudy, K. (2001). The asymmetry hypothesis. Testing the asymmetric relationship between explicitations and implicitations. Paper presented to the Third International Congress of the European Society for Translation Studies. *Claims, Changes and Challenges in Translation Studies*.
- Klaudy, K. (2008). "Explicitation." Mona Baker, Gabriela Saldanha (eds): *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*. London: Routledge, pp. 80-85.
- Levý, J. (2011). *The art of translation* (Vol. 97). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Malmkjær, K., & Windle, K. (Eds.). (2011). *The Oxford handbook of translation studies*. OUP Oxford.
- Munday, J. (2001). *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and Applications*.
- Munday, J. (2016). *Introducing translation studies: Theories and applications*. Routledge.
- Nida, E. A. (1964). *Toward a science of translating*. Leiden: EJ Brill.
- Toury, G. (1995). *Descriptive Translation Studies—and beyond* John Benjamins Publishing Company. *Amsterdam/Philadelphia*.
- Tardzenyuy, N. C. (2016). Revisiting translation strategies and techniques. *International Journal of Comparative Literature and Translation Studies*, 4(4), pp. 48-56.
- Toury, G. (1977). Translational norms and literary translation into Hebrew, pp. 1930-1945. *Tel Aviv: Porter Institute for Poetics and Semiotics*.
- Pym, A. (2014). *Method in translation history*. Routledge.
- Proshina, Z. (2008). *Theory of Translation, 3rd Edition*, Far Eastern University Press, Manila.
- Vandepitte, S. (2013). Meaning in Translation. *Translation and Meaning, Part 9*, Proceedings 5th International Maastricht - Łódź Duo Colloquium on "Translation and Meaning", Held in Maastricht, The Netherlands, (pp. 61 – 89).
- Vinay, J. P., & Darbelnet, J. (1958). *Stylistique comparée du français et de l'anglais [Comparative Stylistics of French and English]*. Paris: Didier.
- Vesterager, A. K. (2017). Explicitation in legal translation—a study of Spanish-into-Danish translation of judgments. *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, 27, pp. 104-123.
- Williams, J., & Chesterman, A. (2014). *The map: a beginner's guide to doing research in translation studies*. Routledge.